
Assessing conditions to scale up private investment in forest restoration¹

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

Unless otherwise noted, we extracted all data used in the analysis from the se.plan dataset (FAO 2023, 2025). se.plan draws spatial data layers from many sources. It uses Google Earth Engine to convert the layers to a common projection and 30-arcsecond resolution. We extracted variables from the se.plan database on March 6, 2023. We used the statistical package Stata (StataCorp 2023) for post-extraction data processing and merging with additional datasets. The resulting dataset and the statistical code for analyzing it are available for download on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15341984>).

1. General information on se.plan

Although our analysis used variables from the se.plan database, it did not entail running the tool itself. se.plan is designed to support large-scale, medium-resolution (~1 km²) forest restoration planning at national and subnational levels. It does not, in its current formulation, support analyses that span multiple countries, nor does its database include all the variables needed for our analysis. We provide the following general information about se.plan in case it is helpful for understanding the tool's dataset.

se.plan was developed by an international team from the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), Spatial Informatics Group, the U.S. SilvaCarbon Program, Duke University, and Peking University, with technical support from the Google Earth Engine team. It is part of FAO's free, open-source suite of spatial analysis tools, the System for

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Earth Observation Data Access, Processing and Analysis for Land Monitoring (SEPAL). Formal development of se.plan began with an inception workshop in July 2020. FAO released an initial version in June 2021 in conjunction with the launch of the UN Decade on Ecosystem Restoration. It has updated the tool regularly since then. External suggestions for updates have come from, among other sources, workshops with international users from multiple countries held in Bangkok, Thailand, in December 2022 and May 2024.

To run se.plan, a user first selects their “area of interest,” which is an entire country or one or more regions within it. The user then rates, on a 1–5 scale, the relative importance of four potential restoration benefits: biodiversity conservation, carbon sequestration, local livelihoods, and wood production. se.plan includes one to two spatial variables that indicate, in biophysical (not monetary) terms, the potential magnitude of each benefit that could be generated if a pixel with degraded forestland (i.e., one with current tree cover < potential tree cover) were successfully restored. se.plan converts the benefits indicators to a common 1–5 scale and weights them by the user-supplied importance ratings to form a restoration value index, also on a 1–5 scale. It divides the index by a spatial variable on restoration cost (= sum of opportunity cost and implementation costs) to form an approximate benefit–cost ratio, again scaled 1–5. It displays an exportable map showing the values of this ratio for pixels within the area of interest. se.plan is customizable, allowing users to impose constraints that limit restoration to pixels with specified ecological or socioeconomic characteristics and to upload their own data layers in lieu of the default ones included in se.plan’s database.

Exercises to ground-truth se.plan’s spatial predictions of restoration suitability have been conducted in Vietnam (Ngoc and Nakalema 2023) and Nepal (Budha 2024, Joshi 2024). The exercises were conducted by local researchers from or in cooperation with national forestry agencies. They drew on field data and local datasets not available to the global se.plan team. They confirmed se.plan’s usefulness for identifying landscapes having FR potential, but they also emphasized that the siting of actual restoration projects within those landscapes must be based on higher-resolution field data and determined in consultation with local communities. In particular, they highlighted the importance of site-level information on forest restoration costs (including land value), land tenure, and management objectives. These findings are consistent with se.plan’s intended purpose to support national and subnational FR planning at the landscape level, not the project level.

2. Defining the sample

Identifying low- and middle-income countries (LMICs)

National and subnational boundaries in se.plan are from the Global Administrative Unit Layers dataset (FAO 2015). We selected countries that the World Bank classified as low or middle income (World Bank, n.d. (a)) in at least two years during 2010–2012, which straddles the 2011 declaration of the Bonn Challenge. The starting dataset, after removing pixels in unsettled territories with disputed boundaries (0.4% of the pixels) and before filtering to identify pixels with restorable forestland, included 88.6 million pixels in 133 low- and middle-income countries (LMICs).

Identifying pixels with restorable forestland outside protected areas (Figure 1 in main text)

We applied a series of five filters to identify pixels with restorable forestland. First, we used se.plan’s ecological zones variable (FAO, 2012) to retain only pixels in zones where trees naturally occur, which we assumed to be all zones with “forest,” “woodland,” or “mountain system” in their names. Within those zones, we used se.plan’s potential tree cover variable to retain only pixels with potential cover greater than 10% of the area, which is the lower bound on FAO’s definition of “forest” (FAO, 2018). The se.plan team drew the potential tree cover variable from Bastin et al. (2019), who developed it using spatial data on 11 topographical, edaphic, and climatic variables and direct interpretation of nearly 80,000 very high resolution (≤ 1 m) satellite images. This initial filtering reduced the number of pixels and countries to 46.5 million and 125, respectively.

Second, to focus on rural land, we used se.plan’s land cover variable, which refers to the dominant land cover in 2019 (Buchhorn et al. 2020), to remove pixels classified as urban areas or permanent water bodies (including snow and ice). This filter reduced the number of pixels and countries to 45.8 million and 120, respectively.

Third, we removed pixels where the opportunity cost of land—the value of land in nonforest use—was so high as to make forest restoration (FR) unlikely to be financially feasible. As discussed below, the se.plan opportunity cost variable refers to the value of land in agricultural use. We removed pixels with an opportunity cost greater than USD 7,200/ha, which is at the high end of commercial timberland values reported in a study by Cubbage et al. (2020).

The study reports 34 estimates of land expectation value (LEV) for timber plantations in LMICs. The estimates follow a relatively smooth distribution aside from the two largest ones, which are substantially larger than the others. We therefore took the third-largest estimate, which was for industrial eucalyptus plantations in Laos, as a more generally applicable estimate of the maximum LEV for timber plantations in LMICs. That estimate was USD 7,200/ha after converting from the authors' 8% discount rate to the 7% rate used in se.plan's opportunity cost layer (see below) and rounding. Applying this threshold value as a filter ruled out restoration on land with a higher value for food production and other forms of agriculture. It reduced the number of pixels and countries to 38.3 million and 117, respectively. A small portion of this reduction (3% of the removed pixels) was due to missing data on either opportunity cost or implementation costs (see below).

Fourth, we used se.plan's current tree cover variable, which refers to the percentage of pixel area with tree cover in 2019 (Buchhorn et al. 2020), to retain only pixels with current tree cover less than potential tree cover. This filter represents our working definition of "forest degradation." It reduced the number of pixels to 21.1 million but did not reduce the number of countries.

The current tree cover variable refers to all types of tree cover, not only naturally regenerated forests, planted forests, and forest plantations as those terms are commonly defined (FAO 2018). It includes orchards and small-scale and large-scale perennial tree-crop plantations (e.g., oil palm, cocoa, coffee, coconut), which common definitions of "forest" exclude. A lack of distinction between these agricultural tree systems and forests as commonly defined is a common feature of remotely sensed global datasets on tree cover (Hansen et al. 2013, Tropek et al. 2014, Gao et al. 2025), but datasets distinguishing different types of tree systems are becoming available (Lesiv et al. 2022, Clinton et al. 2024). Because the current tree cover variable includes these agricultural tree systems, our definition of restorable forestland excludes conversion of them back to forests as commonly defined. This exclusion is reasonable given that these land uses are often more profitable than forest-related uses (Clough et al. 2016), which makes private landholders unlikely to convert them back to forests.

Fifth and finally, we removed pixels located inside protected areas according to se.plan's protected areas variable (UNEP-WCMC and IUCN, n.d.). This filter reduced the number of

pixels and countries to 18.4 million and 115, respectively. A small portion of this reduction (2% of removed pixels) was due to missing data on one or more of the conditions favoring private investment and the application of a one-hectare minimum area threshold for restorable forestland. These minor sample reductions are explained below.

3. Calculating restorable forestland area

Calculating the area of restorable forestland within pixels that we identified as having restorable forestland required additional assumptions about the within-pixel interpretation of se.plan's potential and current tree cover variables. Both variables refer to average values for 30-arcsecond pixels. The potential tree cover variable thus does not indicate whether tree cover under natural conditions would be spread evenly across a pixel or occur in one or more high-density patches within it. The current tree cover variable similarly reveals nothing about the spatial pattern of tree removal within the pixel that caused current tree cover to be less than potential tree cover. At one extreme, the difference between potential and current tree cover could be due to diffuse, incomplete removal of tree cover across the entire pixel, as might happen with selective harvesting of timber or fuelwood. At the other extreme, it could be due to concentrated removal of all tree cover in one part of the pixel with tree cover remaining intact in the rest, as might occur with forest clearing for cropland or pastures.

A 30-arcsecond pixel is small relative to the scale of the 846 ecoregions shown in Figure 1 of Dinerstein et al. (2017), which span areas comparable in scale to states or provinces in LMICs. This scale difference implies that most se.plan pixels are associated with a single naturally occurring forest type. This pixel-level homogeneity in turn implies that se.plan's potential tree cover variable can be interpreted as referring to tree cover being more or less evenly spread within a pixel. For example, if the variable has a value of 0.3 in a hypothetical pixel, then the naturally occurring forest in that pixel would be an open forest with scattered trees that shade 30% of the land surface and are surrounded by openings that collectively account for the remaining 70% of the surface.

Regarding the current tree cover variable, most pixels with restorable forestland have dominant land covers that are associated with heavy removal of naturally occurring tree cover, i.e., cropland and the two land covers assumed to be associated with livestock grazing,

herbaceous vegetation and shrubs (Figure 2 in main text). This pattern implies that the current tree cover variable is better interpreted as referring to remaining tree cover being concentrated in parts of a pixel rather than being diffused across it.

These interpretations suggest that, to a first approximation, the restorable share of a pixel's area can be defined as the fraction with no tree cover:

$$\text{Restorable share} = 1 - (\text{Current tree cover} / \text{Potential tree cover}).$$

The share ranges from 0 when current tree cover equals potential tree cover to 1 when current tree cover equals 0. Continuing the example above, if se.plan's current tree cover variable for the hypothetical pixel has a value of 0.2, then the pixel's restorable share is 0.33 ($= 1 - 0.2/0.3$): the original forest has been removed in one-third of the pixel but remains in the rest. Note that under this definition, the natural openings that account for 70% of the surface area of forestland in the remaining two-thirds of the pixel are not considered to be restorable areas where additional trees can be packed in. The definition thus accounts for variation in canopy cover under natural conditions.

Restorable area is then given by the product of a pixel's restorable share and its area:

$$\text{Restorable area} = \text{Restorable share} \times \text{Pixel area}.$$

Restorable area is less than pixel area except when current tree cover is 0, in which case the two areas are equal.

We dropped pixels with less than one hectare of restorable area, which is below the resolution of se.plan's land cover variable. This restriction reduced the number of pixels slightly, from 18.7 million to 18.5 million, but did not reduce the number of countries (from 117). Supplementary Figure 4 shows the pixels in the final dataset of 18.4 million pixels and 115 countries sorted by their restorable shares. The horizontal axis shows cumulative restorable area, and the vertical axis shows restorable share. Only a small area (< 10%) has a restorable share equal to 1 (no current tree cover). The remaining area is relatively uniformly distributed across restorable share values below 1.

4. Restorable forestland area by income group and 2019 land cover (Figure 2 in main text)

We based the classification of countries by income group—low income (LI), lower middle income (lower MI), and upper middle income (upper MI)—in Figure 2 on the World Bank’s classification for 2022 (World Bank, n.d. (a)), with the exception of four countries whose classification changed from upper MI during 2010–2012 to high income in 2022: Antigua and Barbuda, Chile, Panama, and Uruguay. We retained these four countries in the upper MI group to maintain consistency with their classification when the Bonn Challenge was declared.

We based the land cover classes in the figure on the classes in se.plan’s land cover variable, which refers to 2019 (Buchhorn et al. 2020). “Cropland” is the class labeled “Cultivated and managed vegetation/agriculture (cropland)” in the source data. “Herbaceous vegetation” and “Shrubs” are labels used in the source data. “Forest” combines six classes labeled “Closed forest” and six classes labeled “Open forest” in the source data. “Other” combines two small classes in the source data, “Bare/sparse vegetation” and “Herbaceous wetland.”

5. Conditions favoring private investment (Table 1 and Figure 3 in main text; Supplementary Figure 1)

We drew data for five of the seven investment conditions in the wood-driven base scenario from the se.plan dataset: tree growth rate, market access, FR costs, scale, and property rights. We generated new data for the other two, domestic wood products demand and country risk premium. All were gridded except domestic wood products demand and country risk, which were measured at the country level.

Table 1 in the main text provides summary statistics for these variables in a balanced sample that includes pixels with data on all seven conditions. Data were missing for small numbers of observations for market access (1,555), tree growth rate (5,764), domestic wood products demand (22,371), and scale (24,633). The combined effect of these missing data was to reduce the number of pixels with data on all seven conditions very slightly (to 18.4 million) and to cause two of the 117 countries to be dropped from the sample (Lesotho, Palestine). Figures 2, 3, and 5 in the main text are based on the same balanced sample.

Tree growth rate, market access, and scale

The se.plan variables on tree growth rate and market access are drawn from published studies. Tree growth rate refers to potential annual production of woody biomass by fast-growing trees (e.g., eucalyptus) in dry metric tons per hectare per year growing under rainfed conditions (original resolution 30 arcminutes) (Albanito et al. 2016). The source study estimated these rates by accounting for eco-floristic zones, soil conditions, slope, precipitation, and temperature. Market access refers to travel time in minutes to the nearest city in 2015 (original resolution 30 arcseconds) (Weiss et al. 2018).

Scale is simply the restorable area per capita, which we generated by using variables described above:

$$Scale = Restorable\ area / (1 + Pixel\ area \times Human\ population\ density).$$

The denominator includes 1 to allow calculation of the variable in rare cases of unpopulated pixels (< 0.6% of the total number). This variable is intended to capture potential scale economies associated with FR investments, which could arise from transactions costs, implementation costs, or both being lower on a unit-area basis when tract size is larger. It is a crude measure of scale economies because it ignores the distribution of restorable area across distinct landholdings within a pixel. Consider two hypothetical pixels, each with 50 hectares of restorable forestland and populations of 500 people. In one, all 50 hectares are held by a single person; in the other, each person holds 0.1 hectare. An external forest restoration investor would face a greater challenge in restoring all 50 hectares in the latter case, given the need to coordinate across so many landholders. The distribution of landholdings thus matters, but we know of no dataset that provides reliable information on it at a disaggregated level for LMICs. A global dataset on crop field size, not landholdings, indicates that field size tends to be smaller in LMICs than in high-income countries, with the exception of a few LMICs mostly in South America (Fritz et al. 2015).

Property rights

Property rights is an index ranging from -2.5 (least protection of property rights) to +2.5 (greatest protection of property rights). The se.plan team generated it by using multiple regression to downscale 2015 national data on the World Bank's Rule of Law indicator

(Kaufmann et al. 2010) to Level 1 administrative subdivisions (i.e., states or provinces). The downscaling assumption for this variable and others described below was that the statistical relationship between the variable and predictors at the national level also holds at the subdivision level.

The se.plan team regressed the national Rule of Law indicator on three national variables: the natural logarithm of population density (people per km²) (World Bank, n.d. (b)); the natural logarithm of GDP per capita (constant 2011 US dollars, purchasing power parity) (World Bank, n.d. (b)); and a dummy variable identifying countries with a British colonial history (Becker 2019) (Supplementary Table 3). Colonial history influences legal systems, hence property rights (La Porta, Lopez-de-Silanes, and Shleifer, 2008). Specifications that included additional dummies for other colonial histories (Belgian, Dutch, French, German, Portuguese, Spanish) had reduced variable significance. The team used the estimated regression model and 2015 data on population density and GDP per capita by Level 1 subdivision to predict the property rights index for Level 1 subdivisions, with gridded data used to generate the socioeconomic variables for the subdivisions (CIESIN 2018, Kummur et al. 2018).

Domestic wood products demand and country risk premium

The current version of se.plan is designed to support within-country restoration planning in one country at a time. Hence, it does not include data that vary only at the country level. Our analysis of conditions that favor private investment in forest restoration included two conditions defined at the national level, domestic wood products demand and country risk premium. We generated data on these conditions as follows and then merged them with the se.plan dataset.

We expressed domestic wood products demand as an annual growth rate and generated it in five steps. First, we compiled national data on annual production, import, and export quantities during two 3-year periods, 1999–2001 (post-Asian financial crisis) and 2017–2019 (pre-COVID pandemic), for the eight major categories of processed wood products: sawnwood (coniferous), sawnwood (nonconiferous), veneer sheets, plywood, particle board, fibreboard, paper and paperboard, and wood pellets (including briquettes and other agglomerates) (FAO, n.d. (b)). Second, we used regional wood-processing conversion factors for Africa, Asia, and Latin America to convert all quantities from their original units to roundwood equivalents, expressed in cubic meters (FAO, ITTO, and United Nations, 2020). Third, we calculated annual apparent

domestic consumption of each product as the sum of production and imports minus exports, and we summed across the eight product categories to obtain aggregate apparent consumption of wood products in each country in each year. Fourth, we defined the starting demand level as the mean of apparent consumption during 1999–2001 and the ending demand level as the mean of apparent consumption during 2017–2019. We used three-year means to reduce the effects of short-run demand fluctuations. Finally, we calculated the annual demand growth rate by dividing the natural logarithm of the ratio of consumption in the two periods by the number of intervening years, 18.

A commonly used measure of the country risk premium (CRP) (Damodaran 2022a, 2022b) was available for 2022 for 98 of the LMICs with restorable forestland. This measure is a strictly positive annual percentage value. We imputed it for the remaining LMICs in three steps. First, for countries in the se.plan database, we generated the first principal component of 2021 national data on the World Bank’s six World Governance Indicators (WGIs) (Kaufmann et al. 2010): Voice and Accountability, Political Stability and Absence of Violence/Terrorism, Government Effectiveness, Regulatory Quality, Rule of Law, and Control of Corruption. The first principal component captured 79% of the cross-country variation in the six WGIs and was reasonably highly correlated with the natural logarithm of the CRP ($r = -0.62, p < 0.001$) for the 98 countries with data on both variables. The negative correlation is expected: better governance is associated with lower country risk. Second, we regressed the natural logarithm of the CRP on the first principal component of the WGIs, with dummy variables for World Bank regions and income groups (World Bank, n.d. (a)) included as additional explanatory variables (Supplementary Table 4). We renamed the Europe and Central Asia region “Central Asia” because se.plan excludes countries in Europe. We did not ln-transform the first principal component because it included negative values (approximate range: -5 to $+5$.) Finally, we used the estimated regression equation to impute the missing CRP values.

FR costs: opportunity cost

FR costs in our analysis are the sum of opportunity cost and implementation costs, both drawn from the se.plan dataset. These two cost components refer to reference years 2019 (opportunity cost) and 2011 (implementation costs) and are expressed in constant 2020 US dollars per hectare. Busch et al. (2024) describe in detail the se.plan team’s methods for generating the opportunity

cost variable. We therefore provide only an overview here. We provide more detail on generation of the implementation costs variable, including how we modified it to allow for natural regeneration in the “natural climate solutions” (NCS) scenario, in the following subsection.

The se.plan team assumed that land would be used for agriculture if restoration did not occur. It defined annual opportunity cost as “land rent”: the share of annual agricultural profit attributable to land instead of other production inputs (labor, capital). It capitalized annual land rent to an infinite discounted sum by dividing by 7%, the approximate mean real interest rate across the LMICs in the dataset (World Bank, n.d. (b)). This rate represents a market discount rate, which is more suitable for our analysis than a social discount rate given our focus on private investment.

The se.plan team generated annual land-rent datasets separately for cropland and pastureland. In the case of cropland, it began with 2010 gridded data (original resolution 5 arcminutes) on gross crop revenue per hectare (Yu et al. 2020). It updated these data to 2019 using country-specific ratios of crop revenue per hectare in 2019 compared to 2010 (FAO, n.d. (a)). It converted gross revenue per hectare to land rent per hectare using conversion factors developed by applying econometric methods to farm-level survey data (FAO, n.d. (d)). This process resulted in the spatial units for cropland opportunity cost being given by the intersection of the original cropland revenue grid cells and the boundaries of Level 1 administrative subdivisions. The process for generating the pastureland opportunity cost dataset was similar, except it began with 2010 gridded livestock data (original resolution 5 arcminutes) (FAO, n.d. (c)).

The se.plan team set the overall opportunity cost for a pixel equal to the pixel’s cropland opportunity cost estimate, with missing values or values of zero replaced with the pixel’s pastureland opportunity cost estimate. It prioritized the cropland estimates because the factors for converting gross revenue to land rent were based on many more survey observations (> 40 times) for cropland than for pastureland. In addition, the cropland estimates tended to be higher than the pastureland estimates. Prioritizing the former thus reduced the risk of underestimating opportunity cost and exaggerating the economic feasibility of FR.

FR costs: implementation costs in base scenario

Implementation costs refer to the expense of activities required to regenerate forests. These costs are additional to the opportunity cost of the land where restoration occurs. The se.plan implementation costs variable spans 133 LMICs. It is an aggregate of both: (i) establishment

costs, which are incurred in the first year of restoration and are associated with such activities as site preparation, planting, and fencing; and (ii) management costs, which are associated with monitoring, protection, and other recurrent activities in subsequent years. It includes management costs for the first three to five years after establishment, the assumed age by which regenerated tree stands reach the “free to grow” stage and can outcompete other vegetation.

Given the se.plan assumption that agriculture is the alternative land use for forest restoration, the implementation costs variable in the se.plan dataset refers to planting, not natural regeneration, as natural sources of propagules might not be sufficient for rapid restoration of land that has been cleared for agriculture. As discussed below, we modified this variable to allow for natural regeneration in the NCS scenario.

The se.plan team estimated implementation costs in four steps. It began by collaborating with the World Bank Library to identify World Bank projects initiated during 1992–2019 whose documents included at least one of the following phrases: “forest restoration,” “reforest*,” “afforest*,” “tree planting,” and “watershed rehabilitation.” This process yielded 383 projects. The team added four projects initiated during 1987–1991 that it had identified when evaluating the feasibility of extracting implementation cost data from the Bank’s project documents.

It then manually reviewed the projects’ project appraisal reports (PADs) and implementation completion reports (ICRs) for data on implementation costs. PADs are the primary source of information used by the Bank’s Board of Executive Directors when it determines whether to approve projects for implementation. ICRs play a similar role when the Bank evaluates project performance, typically five years after project inception but often longer. Most of the projects occurred in interior locations (i.e., they excluded mangroves) and aimed at creating stands of trees, ranging from small woodlots to large plantations, not other tree systems such as intercropped agroforestry, silvopasture, shelterbelts, bamboo, and mangroves. Data extraction from the documents thus focused on estimates of implementation costs for tree stands, although some project-wide estimates referred to the composite cost of tree stands on some sites and different tree systems on other sites.

The documents for most projects yielded multiple estimates, such as costs at different project sites, but some yielded just a single estimate, usually the project-wide cost. Most reported an aggregate cost that was not broken down by regeneration activity (site preparation, planting,

fertilizing, ...) or inputs (labor, fuel, seedings, fertilizer, ...). Some reported cost per unit area, while others reported total cost and total area. The team converted all estimates to a cost-per-hectare basis, expressed in constant 2011 US dollars, for further analysis.

This process yielded 233 estimates from 50 projects in 24 LMICs, spanning 1987 to 2019. Estimates were available from both the PAD and the ICR for 13 projects, only the PAD for 34 projects, and only the ICR for three projects. A higher proportion of ICRs would have been preferred, as their cost estimates are based more on actual project performance than are those from the PADs, which report *ex ante* projected costs. World Bank project teams prepare additional documents, but they were available for the 50 projects even less regularly than the ICRs.

The se.plan team classified the projects by country and, where possible, Level 1 subdivision. (The Bank did not begin archiving shapefiles for project sites until after 2010.) Most estimates were from Asia (85%), with many fewer from Latin America (8%) and Africa (7%). The land use prior to regeneration was agriculture for 51% of the estimates, forestry for 32%, and a mix of the two uses for 17%. Regarding regeneration methods, 79% of the estimates referred to artificial regeneration (planting, sowing), 5% to natural regeneration, and 16% to a mix of the two methods. Estimates that were the composite cost of tree stands on some sites and different tree systems on other sites accounted for 13% of the sample. The documents listed multiple intended benefits for most estimates, with wood production mentioned for 82%, watershed or coastal protection for 64%, biodiversity conservation for 40%, carbon sequestration for 32%, and fodder production for 12%. In constant 2011 US dollars (USD), the estimates ranged from USD 37/ha to USD 4,335/ha, with a mean of USD 805/ha, a median of USD 533/ha, and a standard deviation of USD 743/ha.

Next, the team used linear regression to statistically relate the natural logarithm of the implementation cost estimates to a set of variables hypothesized to influence them:

- a. national GDP per capita (World Bank, n.d. (b)), also ln-transformed;
- b. dummy variables distinguishing tropical and subtropical zones from the temperate zone (FAO, 2012);
- c. total regenerated area, also ln-transformed;

- d. a dummy variable distinguishing reforestation from afforestation, with “reforestation” referring to sites that had recently lost their forest cover (e.g., due to wood harvests, wildfires, or storm damage) and had not been converted to a nonforest land use, and “afforestation” referring to sites with a nonforest land use (e.g., agriculture) (FAO, 2018);
- e. a dummy variable distinguishing natural regeneration from planting;
- f. a set of dummy variables indicating estimates that were the composite cost of a mix of tree stands and one of the other tree systems mentioned earlier;
- g. a dummy variable indicating cost estimates that did not include project overhead costs; and
- h. a dummy variable indicating projects with an appraisal year before 2010 (to allow for cost differences pre- and post-Bonn Challenge).

The team used GIS and the information on project location by Level 1 subdivision to construct the variables in categories (a) and (b). It extracted data on the remaining variables from the PADs and ICRs. It ln-transformed the dependent variable in view of results from a Box-Cox analysis ($p = 0.18$ for the null $\theta = 0$). When it estimated the linear regression model, it weighted variables by the inverse number of observations from each project to reduce the influence of projects with a larger number of observations in the sample. It clustered standard errors by project to account for heteroskedasticity and error correlations across observations from the same project (Zeger and Liang 1986). Supplementary Table 5 shows results for the regression model.

Results generally accord with intuition. Implementation costs are positively associated with GDP per capita, which likely reflects labor costs, and negatively associated with total area regenerated, which likely reflects scale economies. They are lower for: natural regeneration than artificial regeneration; estimates that did not include project overhead costs than those that did; and projects that began before 2010 than those that began after. They are higher for reforestation than afforestation, likely due to the World Bank’s reforestation projects prioritizing heavily degraded forests where countries lacked sufficient funding or expertise to restore the forests on their own. They are mostly higher for composite cost estimates, which could reflect project implementation being more complex compared to projects that focused on conventional forest plantations. The se.plan team had no priors on the effects of climate zone. The estimated effects

of the subtropical and tropical dummies were not very precise— $p = 0.098$ and 0.373 , respectively—but the effect sizes were large: the regression coefficients on the subtropical and tropical dummies imply average implementation costs being 36% and 91% higher, respectively, in these zones than in the temperate zone.

In the fourth and final step, the team predicted implementation costs for Level 1 subdivisions by inserting into the estimated regression model estimates of gridded GDP per capita for 2011 (Kummu et al. 2018), the mean of the natural logarithm of total project area in the estimation sample (9.17, or 9,580 ha), and the climate zone variables. It set all other dummy variables in the model equal to 0. It included the climate zone variables despite their low significance in view of their large estimated effects. Spatial differences in implementation costs in the *se.plan* dataset are thus driven by differences in GDP per capita and climate zone. The team redenominated the resulting estimates from constant 2011 US dollars to constant 2020 US dollars.

The estimates ranged from USD 612/ha to USD 4,520/ha, with a mean of USD 1,648/ha, a median of USD 1,519/ha, and a standard deviation of USD 668/ha. The mean, median, and standard deviation refer to observations (pixels) weighted by the restorable area they include. The mean and median estimates are virtually identical to the mean establishment cost reported by Cabbage et al. (2022) for monoculture forest plantations across a mix of 16 LMICs and high-income countries, USD 1,534/ha.

The *se.plan* implementation costs variable has several shortcomings. First, Asia is heavily overrepresented compared to Africa and Latin America in the World Bank project data that underlie its construction. A lack of spatial representativeness of implementation cost data is a common feature of cross-country studies. For example, a study on natural climate solutions (Griscom et al. 2017) used a single implementation cost estimate for the entire globe, which came from a study on forest carbon plantations (Strengers et al. 2008). The latter developed its estimate using just two data sources, whose estimates were almost entirely from the 1990s and from outside LMICs (Bruce et al. 1996, Richards and Stokes 2004). Another global study used as its base estimate the average cost per hectare to restore Brazil's Atlantic forest, with country-level adjustments for the costs of labor and fertilizer relative to those in Brazil (Strassburg et al. 2020). FAO and partner organizations have launched an initiative to compile more consistent and

robust implementation cost data under the UN Decade on Ecosystem Restoration (Bodin et al. 2022).

Second, the data underlying the *se.plan* variable refer solely to World Bank projects, but afforestation and reforestation projects are implemented by a range of private parties (households, communities, companies) and governmental and nongovernmental organizations. A study published after we completed our analysis included implementation cost data from multiple sources in addition to World Bank project documents (Busch et al. 2024). It reported no significant difference in mean implementation costs between World Bank projects and other projects.

Third, the World Bank’s project approval process can be expected to screen out projects in more costly locations. Spatialized estimates based on the costs of Bank projects thus potentially underestimate costs in locations where projects did not occur.

FR costs: implementation costs in NCS scenario

The regression coefficient on the natural regeneration (NR) dummy in Supplementary Table 5 indicates that implementation costs were 66% lower on average for natural regeneration than for planting. This estimate implies the following relationship between implementation costs in the NCS scenario (*Implementation costs_{NCS}*) and the base scenario (*Implementation costs_{Base}*, the planting-based *se.plan* variable):

$$Implementation\ costs_{NCS} = (1 - 0.66 \times NR\ success) \times Implementation\ costs_{Base}.$$

NR success is a *se.plan* variable giving the likelihood (on a 0 to 1 scale) of natural regeneration success (Supplementary Figure 5).

The *se.plan* team developed this variable by inserting the 2019 percentage of forest cover (European Space Agency 2017) in a 5-km buffer around each pixel into a published model that relates landscape variation in natural regeneration success to that percentage (Crouzeilles et al. 2019). Using the expression above, we set *Implementation costs_{NCS}* equal to 34% of *Implementation costs_{Base}* in pixels where natural regeneration was 100% likely to succeed, 100% of *Implementation costs_{Base}* in pixels where natural regeneration was 0% likely to succeed, and intermediate percentages in pixels with values of *NR success* between 0% and 100%.

The resulting estimates of *Implementation costs*_{NCS} ranged from USD 208/ha to USD 4,330/ha, with a mean of USD 1,195/ha, a median of USD 1,053/ha, and a standard deviation of USD 679/ha. The mean, median, and standard deviation refer to observations weighted by restorable areas.

6. Indicators of potential restoration benefits (Figure 4 in main text)

The six benefit indicators in Figure 4 in the main text are expressed in physical terms, not monetary terms. Even as physical indicators, they do not represent explicit predictions of restoration benefits. Rather, they represent *relative* indicators of the *potential* magnitudes of benefits that restoration could provide *if* it were implemented successfully using tree species and forest management practices suitable for supplying those benefits.

We selected the six indicators in Figure 4 because their interpretation as indicators of potential benefits is relatively straightforward and because they are evenly divided between three that pertain more to local livelihood benefits and three that pertain more to global and regional environmental benefits. We acknowledge that other indicators of potential benefits exist. For example, the se.plan dataset includes a biodiversity intactness index (Newbold et al. 2016) in addition to number of threatened species, but the latter is a more commonly used measure of conservation priority. A recently developed dataset on forest-proximate people (Newton et al. 2022) measures the scope for local people to benefit from restoration projects in a more refined manner than the population density variable in Figure 4, but it was not in the se.plan dataset at the time of this analysis.

Benefit indicators from published sources: population density, carbon sequestration, threatened species, and water sufficiency

se.plan's data on four indicators were drawn directly from published sources: 2020 population density (original resolution 30 arcseconds) (CIESIN 2018); 2016 carbon sequestration (original resolution 15 arcseconds) (Walker et al. 2022); 2019 threatened species (original resolution 5 arcminutes) (Jenkins et al. 2013, Pimm et al. 2014); and 2014 water sufficiency (original resolution 5 arcminutes) (Hofste et al. 2019). The water indicator in the original source was expressed as a measure of baseline water stress ranging from 0 to 5. We converted it to a measure of water sufficiency by subtracting the original values from 5.

Benefit indicators developed by se.plan team: forest-sector employment and woodfuel harvests

Compared to population density, these two indicators more directly measure the potential ability of forest restoration to support local livelihoods. Forest-sector employment refers to the number of forest-related jobs per hectare of forest in 2015, summed across three industries: forestry, logging, and related service activities; manufacture of wood and products of wood and cork except furniture; and manufacture of paper and paper products. A higher level of forest-sector employment implies more attractive business conditions for labor-intensive wood harvesting and processing industries, which could potentially expand with additional wood supplies from restored forests. Woodfuel harvests refer to harvests (in m³) per hectare of forest in 2015. A higher level of woodfuel harvests implies greater demand for woodfuel, a leading energy source in rural areas of many LMICs (FAO 2022) that could potentially be supplied by restored forests. The se.plan team generated data on these indicators by using multiple regression to downscale national data to Level 1 administrative subdivisions.

For forest-sector employment, the se.plan team began by compiling national data on annual number of people employed in the three industries during four three-year periods, 1999–2001, 2009–2011, 2014–2016, and 2019–2021 (International Labour Organization n.d.). Data were available for 55 of the LMICs in se.plan but not for all years. For each country, the team calculated total employment in 2000, 2010, 2015, and 2020 by summing employment across the three industries in each available year of the corresponding three-year periods and then taking the mean over the three years. It used three-year means to reduce the effects of short-run employment fluctuations. It converted total employment to employment per hectare by dividing by data on national forest area, which were available for 2000, 2010, 2015, and 2020 (FAO, 2020).

The se.plan team pooled the data across countries and time periods and regressed employment per hectare on three variables—national population density (people per km²) (World Bank, n.d. (b)), national GDP per capita (constant 2011 US dollars) (World Bank n.d. (b)), and the share of planted forests in national forest area (FAO 2020)—with all variables ln-transformed. It included fixed effects for FAO regions (Africa, Asia, North and Central America, Oceania, South America) in the regression model to control for unobserved time-invariant regional factors that affected employment (Supplementary Table 6). It used fixed effects for

regions instead of countries due to many countries being represented by just a single observation in the dataset. Other model specifications, such as ones that included different forest area variables (e.g., area share for production forest) or excluded one or both of the socioeconomic variables, yielded worse fits, reduced variable significance, or both.

In a final step, the team predicted employment per hectare for Level 1 subdivisions by using the estimated regression model and 2015 data on population density and GDP per capita by Level 1 subdivision, with gridded data used to generate the socioeconomic variables for the subdivisions (CIESIN 2018, Kummu et al. 2018). It set the planted forest share equal to its national value, as gridded data on planted forest area were not available when it generated the variable. Such data recently became available (Lesiv et al. 2022) and could be used by the se.plan team to update the variable.

The se.plan team followed a similar process for woodfuel harvests. It began by compiling national data on annual harvests of coniferous and nonconiferous woodfuel (in m³) during the same four three-year periods as for forest-sector employment, 1999–2001, 2009–2011, 2014–2016, and 2019–2021 (FAO n.d. (b)). Data were available for 125 of the LMICs in se.plan in nearly all years. The team calculated total woodfuel harvests in 2000, 2010, 2015, and 2020 by summing harvests of the two woodfuel types and taking the mean for each corresponding three-year period. It used three-year means to reduce the effects of short-run harvest fluctuations. It converted total harvest to harvest per hectare by dividing by national forest area (FAO 2020). It pooled the data across countries and time periods and regressed harvest per hectare on two variables—national population density (people per km²) (World Bank n.d. (b)) and its square—with all variables ln-transformed. It included country fixed effects in the regression model to control for unobserved time-invariant national differences that affected woodfuel consumption (Supplementary Table 7). In a final step, it predicted wood fuel harvest per hectare for Level 1 subdivisions by using the estimated model and 2015 data on population density by Level 1 subdivision, with gridded data used to estimate subdivision population density (CIESIN 2018).

Testing differences between areas with at least four favorable conditions and areas with less than four favorable conditions

We used linear regression to test mean differences in potential benefits between pixels with a larger number of favorable investment conditions and those with a smaller number. For a given

scenario (base or NCS), we generated a dummy variable that equaled 1 for pixels with at least four favorable conditions and 0 for pixels with less than four favorable conditions. We regressed each of the six benefit indicators on the scenario's dummy variable, with pixels weighted by their restorable area and standard errors clustered by Level 1 subdivision to correct for heteroskedasticity and spatial correlation (Zeger and Liang 1986). The rounded number of observations was 18.4 million in all cases, with small differences across models due to missing data.

The dummy variables were significant at $p < 0.01$ for population density and forest-sector employment in both scenarios, $p < 0.01$ for carbon sequestration and threatened species in the NCS scenario, and $p < 0.05$ for threatened species in the base scenario. They were far from significant ($p > 0.15$) for the remaining indicators.

The columns in Figure 4 represent the estimated coefficients on the dummy variables from the 12 regressions (= six indicators \times two scenarios). To make the estimates comparable across indicators, we expressed them as percentages of the indicators' mean values for pixels with less than four favorable conditions. For example, the regression coefficient on the dummy variable for population density in the base scenario was 54.8, indicating that pixels with at least four favorable conditions had on average 54.8 more people per km² than those with less than four favorable conditions. Mean population densities in two groups were 122.8 and 68.0, respectively, which result in the 81% difference shown in Figure 4: $122.8 - 68.0 = 54.8$, and $54.8/68.0 = 81\%$.

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Supplementary Figure 1 | NCS scenario: restorable forestland outside protected areas in LMICs, by number of favorable conditions for private FR investment. LI = low income, MI = middle income. Areas are aggregated across 18.4 million pixels in 115 LMICs.

	Country risk	Property rights	Market access	Tree growth	Scale	Domestic demand
Property rights	0.39					
Market access	0.14	0.45				
Tree growth	0.27	-0.12	-0.08			
Scale	0.17	-0.15	-0.47	0.09		
Domestic demand	-0.47	-0.06	0.02	-0.22	-0.32	
FR costs	-0.25	-0.33	-0.33	-0.38	0.01	0.01

Supplementary Figure 2 | Base scenario: tetrachoric correlations among conditions favoring private FR investment. Dark blue = larger positive (≥ 0.25), light blue = smaller positive ($< 0.25, > 0.1$), gray = near zero ($-0.1-0.1$), light gold = smaller negative ($< -0.1, > -0.25$), dark gold = larger negative (≤ -0.25). Correlations are calculated using binary investment conditions (1 = more favorable, 0 = less favorable) for 18.4 million pixels in 115 LMICs.

	Country risk	Property rights	Market access	Carbon sequestration	Scale
Property rights	0.39				
Market access	0.14	0.45			
Carbon sequestration	-0.04	-0.18	0.12		
Scale	0.17	-0.15	-0.47	-0.36	
FR costs	-0.23	-0.32	-0.35	-0.12	0.02

Supplementary Figure 3 | NCS scenario: tetrachoric correlations among conditions favoring private FR investment. Dark blue = larger positive (≥ 0.25), light blue = smaller positive ($< 0.25, > 0.1$), gray = near zero ($-0.1-0.1$), light gold = smaller negative ($< -0.1, > -0.25$), dark gold = larger negative (≤ -0.25). Correlations are calculated using binary investment conditions (1 = more favorable, 0 = less favorable) for 18.4 million pixels in 115 LMICs.

Supplementary Figure 4 | Restorable share for pixels with restorable forestland in LMICs. A value of 0 indicates that a pixel includes no restorable forestland, while a value of 1 indicates that the entire pixel is restorable forestland. Number of observations: 18.4 million pixels in 115 LMICs.

Supplementary Figure 5 | Likelihood of natural regeneration success across pixels with restorable forestland in LMICs. A value of 0% indicates that natural seed sources are insufficient for natural regeneration to have any chance of restoring a site. Number of observations: 18.4 million pixels in 115 LMICs.

Supplementary Table 1 | Base scenario: restorable forestland area by country, sorted in descending order by area with four or more (4+) favorable conditions for private FR investment. Income groups: LI = low income; MI = middle income. Regions: CA = Central Asia; EAP = East Asia & Pacific; LAC = Latin America & Caribbean; MENA = Middle East & North Africa; SA = South Asia; SSA = Sub-Saharan Africa.

Country	Income group	Region	Restorable forestland ('000 ha)		
			Total	4+ favorable conditions	< 4 favorable conditions
Brazil	Upper MI	LAC	157,077	101,681	55,396
Argentina	Upper MI	LAC	60,626	49,106	11,520
India	Lower MI	SA	49,221	48,797	424
China	Upper MI	EAP	46,016	43,981	2,035
Colombia	Upper MI	LAC	20,916	17,447	3,469
Mexico	Upper MI	LAC	17,738	14,324	3,414
South Africa	Upper MI	SSA	15,341	12,541	2,800
Iran	Lower MI	MENA	13,046	12,022	1,024
Turkey	Upper MI	CA	29,164	11,478	17,686
Indonesia	Lower MI	EAP	14,396	9,629	4,766
Uruguay	Upper MI	LAC	9,199	9,075	125
Paraguay	Upper MI	LAC	11,668	8,685	2,983
Bolivia	Lower MI	LAC	16,856	6,966	9,889
Angola	Lower MI	SSA	27,697	6,803	20,894
Peru	Upper MI	LAC	7,087	6,298	789
Kazakhstan	Upper MI	CA	6,173	5,933	240
Madagascar	LI	SSA	23,924	5,607	18,317
Ethiopia	LI	SSA	19,892	5,374	14,517
Venezuela	Lower MI	LAC	10,426	4,707	5,719
Chile	Upper MI	LAC	6,618	4,267	2,351
Côte d'Ivoire	Lower MI	SSA	6,410	4,254	2,157
Tanzania	Lower MI	SSA	11,912	4,113	7,799
Thailand	Upper MI	EAP	8,658	3,988	4,669
Uganda	LI	SSA	6,042	3,971	2,071
Ghana	Lower MI	SSA	7,406	3,779	3,627
Morocco	Lower MI	MENA	3,871	3,699	172
Namibia	Upper MI	SSA	5,484	3,325	2,159
Algeria	Lower MI	MENA	3,237	3,216	21
Myanmar	Lower MI	EAP	10,162	2,845	7,317
Mozambique	LI	SSA	13,982	2,833	11,149
Bangladesh	Lower MI	SA	2,689	2,688	1
Botswana	Upper MI	SSA	2,583	2,583	0
Kenya	Lower MI	SSA	4,299	2,565	1,735

Philippines	Lower MI	EAP	4,118	2,241	1,877
Dem Rep of the Congo	LI	SSA	15,828	2,163	13,665
Georgia	Upper MI	CA	1,765	1,677	87
Viet Nam	Lower MI	EAP	1,854	1,672	182
Benin	Lower MI	SSA	3,591	1,620	1,971
Malaysia	Upper MI	EAP	1,616	1,582	34
Panama	Upper MI	LAC	1,884	1,490	394
Guatemala	Upper MI	LAC	1,767	1,472	295
Zambia	LI	SSA	12,944	1,369	11,575
Guinea	LI	SSA	6,325	1,341	4,984
Azerbaijan	Upper MI	CA	1,271	1,177	94
Congo	Lower MI	SSA	4,831	1,139	3,692
Guyana	Upper MI	LAC	1,155	1,113	41
Nicaragua	Lower MI	LAC	3,267	1,033	2,234
Sudan	LI	SSA	2,191	964	1,226
Ecuador	Upper MI	LAC	3,399	942	2,457
Senegal	Lower MI	SSA	4,340	865	3,475
Costa Rica	Upper MI	LAC	1,070	858	211
Rwanda	LI	SSA	1,250	822	428
Gabon	Upper MI	SSA	920	814	105
Uzbekistan	Lower MI	CA	1,848	813	1,035
Armenia	Upper MI	CA	943	812	131
Cameroon	Lower MI	SSA	6,922	590	6,332
Yemen	LI	MENA	1,517	586	931
Honduras	Lower MI	LAC	2,257	583	1,674
Haiti	Lower MI	LAC	1,194	575	619
Sierra Leone	LI	SSA	1,644	507	1,137
Papua New Guinea	Lower MI	EAP	1,207	496	711
Kyrgyzstan	Lower MI	CA	6,633	470	6,164
Nigeria	Lower MI	SSA	28,504	430	28,075
Sri Lanka	Lower MI	SA	601	401	200
Nepal	Lower MI	SA	2,584	383	2,201
Togo	LI	SSA	1,909	345	1,564
Malawi	LI	SSA	4,102	331	3,771
South Sudan	LI	SSA	5,188	323	4,865
Liberia	LI	SSA	538	318	220
Mali	LI	SSA	11,592	313	11,278
Belize	Upper MI	LAC	438	299	139
Dominican Republic	Upper MI	LAC	351	283	68
Afghanistan	LI	SA	8,377	233	8,144
Libya	Upper MI	MENA	261	231	31
Fiji	Upper MI	EAP	257	227	30

Suriname	Upper MI	LAC	215	202	13
Timor-Leste	Lower MI	EAP	243	193	51
Turkmenistan	Upper MI	CA	192	176	16
Mongolia	Lower MI	EAP	13,169	165	13,004
Pakistan	Lower MI	SA	940	154	786
Cuba	Upper MI	LAC	2,948	152	2,796
Eswatini	Lower MI	SSA	454	119	335
Mauritius	Upper MI	SSA	112	112	0
El Salvador	Lower MI	LAC	789	101	688
Bhutan	Lower MI	SA	99	80	19
Gambia	LI	SSA	579	77	503
Cambodia	Lower MI	EAP	1,262	76	1,185
Iraq	Upper MI	MENA	269	51	218
French Guiana	Upper MI	LAC	46	44	2
Jordan	Upper MI	MENA	32	31	0
Tunisia	Lower MI	MENA	1,544	26	1,518
Tajikistan	Lower MI	CA	1,490	22	1,468
Vanuatu	Lower MI	EAP	57	20	36
Central African Republic	LI	SSA	5,457	17	5,440
Zimbabwe	Lower MI	SSA	10,996	12	10,984
Lebanon	Lower MI	MENA	306	9	297
Solomon Islands	Lower MI	EAP	38	9	29
Jamaica	Upper MI	LAC	133	5	127
Sao Tome and Principe	Lower MI	SSA	4	4	0
Lao People's Dem Rep	Lower MI	EAP	477	3	474
Antigua and Barbuda	Upper MI	LAC	6	2	4
Dominica	Upper MI	LAC	4	1	3
Dem People's Rep Korea	LI	EAP	991	1	990
Niger	LI	SSA	183	0	183
Somalia	LI	SSA	198	0	198
Burkina Faso	LI	SSA	9,802	0	9,802
Chad	LI	SSA	9,776	0	9,776
Eritrea	LI	SSA	1,742	0	1,742
Burundi	LI	SSA	1,145	0	1,145
Guinea-Bissau	LI	SSA	490	0	490
Syrian Arab Republic	LI	MENA	385	0	385
Cape Verde	Lower MI	SSA	191	0	191
Grenada	Upper MI	LAC	4	0	4
Saint Vincent and the Grenadines	Upper MI	LAC	3	0	3
Saint Lucia	Upper MI	LAC	1	0	1

Supplementary Table 2 | NCS scenario: restorable forestland area by country, sorted in descending order by area with four or more (4+) favorable conditions for private FR investment. Income groups: LI = low income; MI = middle income. Regions: CA = Central Asia; EAP = East Asia & Pacific; LAC = Latin America & Caribbean; MENA = Middle East & North Africa; SA = South Asia; SSA = Sub-Saharan Africa.

Country	Income group	Region	Restorable forestland ('000 ha)		
			Total	4+ favorable conditions	< 4 favorable conditions
Brazil	Upper MI	LAC	156,901	81,545	75,356
India	Lower MI	SA	49,129	36,352	12,776
China	Upper MI	EAP	45,962	28,348	17,614
Colombia	Upper MI	LAC	20,867	16,170	4,697
Mexico	Upper MI	LAC	17,722	14,822	2,900
South Africa	Upper MI	SSA	15,340	13,478	1,862
Indonesia	Lower MI	EAP	14,364	8,692	5,672
Iran	Lower MI	MENA	13,045	5,283	7,762
Argentina	Upper MI	LAC	60,528	4,679	55,849
Zambia	LI	SSA	12,937	4,392	8,546
Uruguay	Upper MI	LAC	9,198	4,379	4,819
Chile	Upper MI	LAC	6,613	4,361	2,252
Nigeria	Lower MI	SSA	28,486	4,037	24,448
Venezuela	Lower MI	LAC	10,404	3,912	6,492
Kazakhstan	Upper MI	CA	6,172	3,651	2,521
Paraguay	Upper MI	LAC	11,667	3,511	8,157
Namibia	Upper MI	SSA	5,484	3,413	2,071
Thailand	Upper MI	EAP	8,652	3,229	5,424
Peru	Upper MI	LAC	7,082	2,906	4,176
Morocco	Lower MI	MENA	3,870	2,867	1,004
Bangladesh	Lower MI	SA	2,665	2,478	187
Botswana	Upper MI	SSA	2,498	2,403	95
Algeria	Lower MI	MENA	3,236	2,306	930
Philippines	Lower MI	EAP	4,108	2,197	1,910
Turkey	Upper MI	CA	29,157	2,099	27,058
Malaysia	Upper MI	EAP	1,615	1,592	23
Senegal	Lower MI	SSA	4,340	1,490	2,850
Panama	Upper MI	LAC	1,882	1,481	402
Ecuador	Upper MI	LAC	3,396	1,277	2,120
Cameroon	Lower MI	SSA	6,917	1,274	5,643
Angola	Lower MI	SSA	27,697	1,162	26,535
Georgia	Upper MI	CA	1,764	1,107	657
Ghana	Lower MI	SSA	7,396	1,038	6,358

Myanmar	Lower MI	EAP	10,131	992	9,139
Tanzania	Lower MI	SSA	11,906	900	11,006
Côte d'Ivoire	Lower MI	SSA	6,408	862	5,546
Benin	Lower MI	SSA	3,591	806	2,785
Kenya	Lower MI	SSA	4,298	766	3,533
Azerbaijan	Upper MI	CA	1,271	713	557
Viet Nam	Lower MI	EAP	1,853	688	1,165
Guatemala	Upper MI	LAC	1,767	648	1,118
Honduras	Lower MI	LAC	2,257	647	1,610
Guyana	Upper MI	LAC	1,154	603	551
Zimbabwe	Lower MI	SSA	10,996	568	10,428
Uganda	LI	SSA	6,037	562	5,475
Tunisia	Lower MI	MENA	1,543	517	1,026
Armenia	Upper MI	CA	943	503	440
Nepal	Lower MI	SA	2,584	477	2,107
Mozambique	LI	SSA	13,958	448	13,510
Bolivia	Lower MI	LAC	16,838	443	16,395
Costa Rica	Upper MI	LAC	1,069	297	773
Mongolia	Lower MI	EAP	13,168	295	12,873
Dominican Republic	Upper MI	LAC	351	290	62
Belize	Upper MI	LAC	436	273	163
Gambia	LI	SSA	579	264	315
Eswatini	Lower MI	SSA	454	253	201
Libya	Upper MI	MENA	261	243	18
El Salvador	Lower MI	LAC	789	201	588
Guinea	LI	SSA	6,325	192	6,132
Cuba	Upper MI	LAC	2,946	186	2,760
Fiji	Upper MI	EAP	255	170	85
Pakistan	Lower MI	SA	937	162	776
Uzbekistan	Lower MI	CA	1,848	125	1,722
Mauritius	Upper MI	SSA	112	100	12
Sudan	LI	SSA	2,191	97	2,094
Dem Rep of the Congo	LI	SSA	15,815	79	15,736
Bhutan	Lower MI	SA	99	77	22
South Sudan	LI	SSA	5,188	71	5,116
Timor-Leste	Lower MI	EAP	243	68	175
Sri Lanka	Lower MI	SA	599	58	541
Nicaragua	Lower MI	LAC	3,267	57	3,210
Papua New Guinea	Lower MI	EAP	1,202	56	1,146
Congo	Lower MI	SSA	4,829	53	4,776
Gabon	Upper MI	SSA	920	53	867
Ethiopia	LI	SSA	19,891	47	19,843

Mali	LI	SSA	11,587	43	11,544
Madagascar	LI	SSA	23,917	38	23,879
Suriname	Upper MI	LAC	215	36	179
Lebanon	Lower MI	MENA	306	36	270
French Guiana	Upper MI	LAC	46	30	16
Vanuatu	Lower MI	EAP	57	18	38
Turkmenistan	Upper MI	CA	192	16	176
Central African Republic	LI	SSA	5,457	15	5,441
Chad	LI	SSA	9,775	15	9,761
Malawi	LI	SSA	4,102	15	4,087
Jordan	Upper MI	MENA	32	11	20
Burkina Faso	LI	SSA	9,802	7	9,795
Jamaica	Upper MI	LAC	133	6	127
Haiti	Lower MI	LAC	1,193	5	1,188
Kyrgyzstan	Lower MI	CA	6,633	4	6,629
Sierra Leone	LI	SSA	1,643	4	1,640
Cape Verde	Lower MI	SSA	191	3	187
Tajikistan	Lower MI	CA	1,488	3	1,484
Lao People's Dem Rep	Lower MI	EAP	477	3	474
Cambodia	Lower MI	EAP	1,259	2	1,257
Yemen	LI	MENA	1,517	2	1,514
Antigua and Barbuda	Upper MI	LAC	6	2	4
Sao Tome and Principe	Lower MI	SSA	4	2	2
Dem People's Rep Korea	LI	EAP	990	1	989
Dominica	Upper MI	LAC	4	1	3
Liberia	LI	SSA	538	1	537
Rwanda	LI	SSA	1,250	0	1,249
Guinea-Bissau	LI	SSA	489	0	489
Togo	LI	SSA	1,908	0	1,908
Solomon Islands	Lower MI	EAP	38	0	37
Syrian Arab Republic	LI	MENA	383	0	383
Afghanistan	LI	SA	8,376	0	8,376
Iraq	Upper MI	MENA	269	0	269
Eritrea	LI	SSA	1,742	0	1,742
Burundi	LI	SSA	1,145	0	1,145
Somalia	LI	SSA	198	0	198
Niger	LI	SSA	183	0	183
Grenada	Upper MI	LAC	4	0	4
Saint Vincent and the Grenadines	Upper MI	LAC	3	0	3
Saint Lucia	Upper MI	LAC	1	0	1

*Supplementary Table 3 | Linear regression results: national variation in property rights (2015).
 Dependent variable: World Bank's Rule of Law governance indicator. Number of observations:
 125 countries. $R^2 = 0.286$, $F(3, 121) = 16.1$ ($p < 0.001$). Robust standard errors.*

Variable	Coefficient	Std. error	t	p
ln(GDP per capita)	0.283	0.0499	5.67	0.000
ln(Population density)	0.0719	0.0399	1.80	0.074
Dummy: British colonial history	0.278	0.105	2.66	0.009
Constant	-3.32	0.436	-7.61	0.000

Supplementary Table 4 | Linear regression results: national variation in country risk premium (2022). Dependent variable: $\ln(\text{country risk premium})$. Number of observations: 20,143,292 pixels. $R^2 = 0.584$, $F(8, 97) = 20.4$ ($p < 0.001$). Robust standard errors are clustered by country (98 clusters). Omitted dummy variables: Central Asia for World Bank region, low income for World Bank income group.

Variable	Coefficient	Std. error	t	p
1 st principal component: World Governance Indicators	-0.129	0.0579	-2.22	0.029
Dummy: East Asia & Pacific	-1.17	0.400	-2.92	0.004
Dummy: Latin America & Caribbean	-0.210	0.324	-0.65	0.519
Dummy: Middle East & North Africa	-0.955	0.324	-2.95	0.004
Dummy: South Asia	-1.21	0.366	-3.30	0.001
Dummy: Sub-Saharan Africa	-0.468	0.310	-1.51	0.134
Dummy: Lower middle income	-0.237	0.120	-1.97	0.052
Dummy: Upper middle income	-0.974	0.281	-3.47	0.001
Constant	-1.62	0.344	-4.70	0.000

Supplementary Table 5 | Linear regression results: variation in implementation costs across World Bank afforestation and reforestation projects. Dependent variable: ln(implementation costs per hectare, constant 2011 US dollars). Number of observations: 233 cost estimates. $R^2 = 0.497$, $F(13, 49) = 17.2$ ($p < 0.0001$). Robust standard errors clustered by World Bank project (50 clusters).

Variable	Coefficient	Std. error	t	p
ln(GDP per capita)	0.322	0.103	3.11	0.003
Dummy: tropical	0.306	0.340	0.90	0.373
Dummy: subtropical	0.645	0.382	1.69	0.098
ln(Area regenerated)	-0.251	0.0602	-4.17	0.000
Dummy: reforestation	0.369	0.176	2.10	0.041
Dummy: natural regeneration	-1.08	0.247	-4.37	0.000
Dummy: partly agroforestry	0.517	0.298	1.73	0.089
Dummy: partly silvopasture	0.616	0.380	1.62	0.112
Dummy: partly shelterbelt	-0.810	0.280	-2.89	0.006
Dummy: partly mangrove	0.685	0.340	2.02	0.049
Dummy: partly bamboo	1.05	0.254	4.13	0.000
Dummy: no overhead	-2.69	0.622	-4.33	0.000
Dummy: project started before 2010	-0.804	0.200	-4.02	0.000
Constant	6.41	1.13	5.68	0.000

Supplementary Table 6 | Linear regression results: national variation in forest-sector employment (2000, 2010, 2015, 2020). Dependent variable: ln(forest-sector employment per hectare). Number of observations: 111 countries by year; highly imbalanced panel, with 55 countries and four years: 2000, 2010, 2015, 2020. $R^2 = 0.799$, $F(3, 54) = 53.7$ ($p < 0.0001$). Robust standard errors are clustered by country (55 clusters). Model includes fixed effects for FAO regions (Africa, Asia, North and Central America, Oceania, South America).

Variable	Coefficient	Std. error	t	p
ln(Population density)	0.739	0.0970	7.61	0.000
ln(GDP per capita)	-0.402	0.151	-2.66	0.010
ln(planted forest area as share of total forest area)	6.53	1.64	3.99	0.000
Constant	-4.84	1.50	-3.23	0.002

Supplementary Table 7 | Linear regression results: national variation in woodfuel harvests (2000, 2010, 2015, 2020). Dependent variable: ln(woodfuel harvest per hectare). Number of observations: 495 countries by year; nearly balanced panel with 125 countries and four years: 2000, 2010, 2015, 2020. $R^2 = 0.976$, $F(2, 124) = 25.7$ ($p < 0.0001$). Robust standard errors are clustered by country (125 clusters). Model includes fixed effects for countries.

Variable	Coefficient	Std. error	t	p
ln(Population density)	1.22	0.250	4.87	0.000
ln(Population density) ²	-0.0764	0.0357	-2.14	0.034
Constant	-3.95	0.513	-7.70	0.000

Supplementary Table 8 / Base scenario: comparison of national FR commitments under Bonn Challenge to restorable forestland area by country, sorted in descending order by commitment area. Blue: commitment area is less than restorable forestland area. Yellow: commitment area is greater than restorable forestland area. Income groups: LI = low income; MI = middle income. Regions: CA = Central Asia; EAP = East Asia & Pacific; LAC = Latin America & Caribbean; MENA = Middle East & North Africa; SA = South Asia; SSA = Sub-Saharan Africa. Sources: Global Restoration Information Hub (2024) for national commitments; author estimates for restorable forestland.

Country	Income group	Region	Commitment ('000 ha)	Restorable forestland ('000 ha)	
				Total	4+ favorable conditions
India	Lower MI	SA	26,000	49,221	48,797
Ethiopia	LI	SSA	15,000	19,892	5,374
Sudan	LI	SSA	14,600	2,191	964
Cameroon	Lower MI	SSA	12,063	6,922	590
Mali	LI	SSA	10,000	11,592	313
Mexico	Upper MI	LAC	8,468	17,738	14,324
Dem Rep of the Congo	LI	SSA	8,000	15,828	2,163
Tanzania	Lower MI	SSA	5,200	11,912	4,113
Kenya	Lower MI	SSA	5,100	4,299	2,565
Burkina Faso	LI	SSA	5,000	9,802	0
Chad	LI	SSA	5,000	9,776	0
Côte d'Ivoire	Lower MI	SSA	5,000	6,410	4,254
Malawi	LI	SSA	4,500	4,102	331
Brazil	Upper MI	LAC	4,280	157,077	101,681
Nigeria	Lower MI	SSA	4,000	28,504	430
Madagascar	LI	SSA	4,000	23,924	5,607
South Africa	Upper MI	SSA	3,600	15,341	12,541
Central African Republic	LI	SSA	3,500	5,457	17
Peru	Upper MI	LAC	3,200	7,087	6,298
Niger	LI	SSA	3,200	183	0
Nicaragua	Lower MI	LAC	2,700	3,267	1,033
Uganda	LI	SSA	2,500	6,042	3,971
Turkey	Upper MI	CA	2,300	29,164	11,478
Zimbabwe	Lower MI	SSA	2,000	10,996	12
Ghana	Lower MI	SSA	2,000	7,406	3,779
Guinea	LI	SSA	2,000	6,325	1,341
Congo	Lower MI	SSA	2,000	4,831	1,139
Senegal	Lower MI	SSA	2,000	4,340	865
Burundi	LI	SSA	2,000	1,145	0
Chile	Upper MI	LAC	1,500	6,618	4,267
Kazakhstan	Upper MI	CA	1,500	6,173	5,933

Togo	LI	SSA	1,400	1,909	345
Honduras	Lower MI	LAC	1,300	2,257	583
Guatemala	Upper MI	LAC	1,200	1,767	1,472
Argentina	Upper MI	LAC	1,000	60,626	49,106
Colombia	Upper MI	LAC	1,000	20,916	17,447
Mozambique	LI	SSA	1,000	13,982	2,833
Panama	Upper MI	LAC	1,000	1,884	1,490
Costa Rica	Upper MI	LAC	1,000	1,070	858
Pakistan	Lower MI	SA	1,000	940	154
Liberia	LI	SSA	1,000	538	318
Bangladesh	Lower MI	SA	750	2,689	2,688
Sierra Leone	LI	SSA	700	1,644	507
Mongolia	Lower MI	EAP	600	13,169	165
Benin	Lower MI	SSA	500	3,591	1,620
Ecuador	Upper MI	LAC	500	3,399	942
Uzbekistan	Lower MI	CA	500	1,848	813
Eswatini	Lower MI	SSA	500	454	119
Cuba	Upper MI	LAC	465	2,948	152
Gambia	LI	SSA	450	579	77
Kyrgyzstan	Lower MI	CA	323	6,633	470
Azerbaijan	Upper MI	CA	270	1,271	1,177
Uruguay	Upper MI	LAC	200	9,199	9,075
Sri Lanka	Lower MI	SA	200	601	401
Dominican Republic	Upper MI	LAC	187	351	283
Belize	Upper MI	LAC	130	438	299
Tajikistan	Lower MI	CA	66	1,490	22
Armenia	Upper MI	CA	50	943	812
Georgia	Upper MI	CA	9	1,765	1,677